

Role of Election Commission to Prevent Political Disinformation From Luring The Voters: With Reference to Punjab Assembly Elections 2022

Paper Id : 18347 Submission Date : 11/12/2023 Acceptance Date : 20/12/2023 Publication Date : 25/12/2023
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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.10430060

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Abstract

A crucial milestone in India's democratic development turned into the Punjab Assembly Elections of 2022, which have been plagued by the continual chance of politically incorrect information. In these political circumstances, the Election Commission of India's (ECI) duty to uphold electoral integrity has become crucial, highlighting the pressing need for technological improvements. This research examines a way to enhance the ECI's policies to better guard citizens against the vast outcomes of politically incorrect information as it delves deeply into the Punjab Assembly Elections 2022 tapestry. It reveals a sturdy association, highlighting the fact that the ECI's capability to shield the electorate from the seductive composition of electoral misinformation is inextricably connected to the efficacy of its technique. It is quite evident that there's no room for enhancement, particularly in regions like voter attention, brief refutation of fake records, rigorous tracking of social media websites, and the escalation of sanctions against those who unfold incorrect information. Finally, the Punjab Assembly Elections of 2022 exhibit the important function performed by the ECI in maintaining the integrity of the election procedure. By filling up those quantitative holes, the ECI can enhance its position as a protector of voters and make sure that the toxic consequences of political misinformation don't deface the democratic material of our country.

Keywords Punjab Assembly Elections 2022, Political Misinformation, Election Commission of India, Electoral Integrity, Technological Improvements, Voter Awareness.

Introduction

Political disinformation

It can be succinctly defined as the practical spread of misguided or misleading statistics in the political arena. It functions as a strategic weapon, with its proponents purposefully using fabrications or distorted facts to accomplish certain goals like altering public opinion, controlling political discourse, or impacting election outcomes. Political misinformation, instead of well-known incorrect information, which covers an extensive variety of incorrect records, targets politicians directly with exaggerated memories, altered facts, or unproven rumours. Politically incorrect information can be prominent on the whole because of the numerous reasons people spread it. Others may also use it to undermine public self-assurance in political bodies, promote dissension among many members of the population, or harm the image of political men and women or events. Some humans may use it to attain their very own political goals. Political misinformation is disseminated through an extensive range of media, together with conventional media, the huge social media platform surroundings, and personal encounters. Importantly, politically incorrect information often takes advantage of the unconscious prejudices and feelings that people are born with. It skilfully exploits underlying prejudices or ideas, making it a totally powerful device for those trying to sway election results and form public opinion. As a result, it poses a critical danger to the balloting device's integrity, which is the inspiration of all democratic regimes internationally. Political misinformation mitigation calls for a diverse approach related to thorough fact-checking, media literacy campaigns, and legislative measures painstakingly designed to thwart the spread of deceptive facts. But as verbal exchange and generation hold to advance, there are always new demanding

situations that have to be overcome within the fight in opposition to this pernicious phenomenon.

Role of The ECI In Preventing Political Disinformation

During the Punjab Assembly Elections in 2022, the Election Commission of India (ECI) ramped up its efforts to counteract political disinformation. Here is how they approached the trouble:

1. Alert Social Media Monitoring Teams: The ECI puts together expert teams with the duty of carefully looking at the social media environment. These devoted groups searched social media websites like Facebook, Twitter, and WhatsApp for any misleading or incorrect election-associated content. Their venture turned into a way to perceive those lies and document them right away.

2. Reliable Fact-Checking Platform: The ECI created a straightforward fact-checking platform to assure the veracity of political assertions. Voters might publish allegations about the use of this device for intensity verification. In order to carry out thorough evaluations, the ECI additionally collaborated with unbiased reality-checking groups. The data was then revealed in an authorized manner.

3. Public Knowledge Drive: The ECI released a huge campaign after understanding the need to raise public expertise. Voters have been made aware of the risks associated with incorrect political information. This complete campaign protected postings on social media as well as advertising on TV and the radio. A dedicated website became a useful tool, teaching site visitors how to spot and counter political disinformation.

4. Aggressive Action Over Disinformation Authors: The ECI wasn't supposed twice to use its electricity in opposition to human beings and organizations that disseminated false records. Candidates and political events had been issued sturdy warnings for carrying out such conduct. Due to their role in spreading misleading statistics, numerous humans were prevented from casting votes in the elections. [Election Commission of India. (2022). Handbook on Election Law and Procedure. New Delhi: Election Commission of India.]

During the Punjab Assembly Elections in 2022, the dissemination of politically incorrect information was greatly slowed by these bold steps. However, it is essential to recognize that the trouble still exists on a larger scale in India. In order to keep the fight against politically incorrect information and maintain the legitimacy of the next elections, collaboration between the ECI and different stakeholders continues to be crucial.

The following examples demonstrate the performance of the ECI's indicators: -

The social media surveillance teams had been vital in speedy seeing and disclosing incidents of politically incorrect information, which allowed for the taking of essential action against the offenders.

The truth-checking provider efficaciously refuted unfaithful statements, consisting of guidelines that a candidate had engaged in criminal behaviour, and provided the electorate with correct statistics through legitimate channels.

Voters received critical know-how from the public focus marketing campaign, letting them spot erroneous statistics online and document incidents of incorrect information for the ECI.

The ECI's efforts had been a success in lessening the impact of political misinformation all through the Punjab Assembly Elections in 2022, but inside the Indian context, the requirement for ongoing cooperation, voter training, and the introduction of modern-day counter-incorrect information processes stays vital.

Importance of Preventing Political Disinformation During Elections

It is crucial to shield against politically incorrect information all through elections for the subsequent motives:

1. Protecting Democratic Morals: The foundation of democracy is the idea of free and fair elections. This important virtue is in danger because of politically incorrect information, which distorts the records, may alter election outcomes, and undermines democracy in its purest form.

2. Upholding Public Confidence: The foundation of each election system is belief. When incorrect information is spread broadly, it undermines public belief in the integrity of elections. The lack of consideration may bring about lower voter turnout and a sense of disengagement from the electoral system.

3. Promoting Social Harmonies: Misinformation regularly exploits social divisions already present, heightening tensions and tearing apart groups. We may march toward an extra-integrated and united society free from the polarizing consequences of incorrect information by fighting political misinformation.

4. Enabling Informed Choices: A colourful democracy relies on knowledgeable citizens. The statistical surroundings are muddled with the aid of misinformation, making it difficult for individuals to distinguish truth from fiction. By preventing this misinformation, we give electorate the ability to make updated logical choices.

5. National Sovereignty: Politically incorrect information every now and then poses a bigger risk to a rustic's protection. External parties may additionally use fake election information to undermine the political equilibrium and protection of a state.

6. Upholding the rule of regulation: If misinformation is allowed to be preserved, it would lead to civil unrest or violent outbursts. Therefore, stopping political incorrect information becomes important for shielding the guidelines of regulation and making sure that elections are held in a peaceful manner.

7. Establishing Honest Election Results: A democracy's foundation is its capability to hold fair elections. By getting rid of incorrect information, we guarantee that election consequences accurately represent the desires of the people as a whole, as opposed to being manipulated via misleading facts.

In conclusion, avoiding political incorrect information at some stage in elections is vital for maintaining democratic concepts, encouraging public consideration, promoting social cohesion, allowing informed citizenship, protecting country-wide security, upholding the rule of regulation, and safeguarding the validity of the consequences of elections.

Aim of study

1. To evaluate the achievement of the steps taken by means of the Indian Election Commission to stop politically incorrect information from attracting the electorates at some point in the Punjab Assembly Elections in 2022.

2. To determine the common type of political disinformation that had been disseminated during the 2022 Punjab Assembly Elections.

3. To examine how politically incorrect information affected the choices made by voters in the Punjab Assembly Elections of 2022.

4. To offer suggestions for the Indian Election Commission on how to boost its capability of averting politically incorrect information from engaging the electorate.

Review of Literature

Brief Overview of the Punjab Assembly Elections 2022

Unquestionably, the Punjab Assembly Elections of 2022 represented a turning point in Indian politics. By a huge majority, the Aam Aadmi Party (AAP) deposed the contemporary president of the Indian National Congress (INC) in a powerful win. This victory marked the end of the INC's rule in Punjab, in addition to the AAP's successful growth outside of Delhi.

The stunning victory of the AAP was made viable through numerous elements. The electorate responded favourably to its promise of radical exchange, unwavering commitment to healthcare and training, and a regular anti-corruption attitude. Additionally, the celebration skilfully tapped into the overall anti-incumbency temper against the INC.

On the other hand, the INC's defeat was a first-rate setback for the birthday celebration, which had been struggling with a run of electoral setbacks in preceding years. The party's possibilities of triumphing in elections have been harmed by internal war and claims of misconduct in the government department, in addition to the challenge of connecting with human beings at the grass-roots level.

Equally disappointing turned into the Bharatiya Janata Party's (BJP) showing in the Punjab Assembly Elections of 2022. In stark competition to its previous document of 23 seats inside the final meeting elections, the birthday party was the handiest capable of acquiring two seats. This loss raised questions about the BJP's plans to increase its electricity in northern India.

The Punjab Assembly Elections of 2022 had long-awaited effects on the U.S.'s political panorama. The AAP's beautiful win gave the birthday celebration a new existence and improved its probabilities for the next popular election in India in 2024. On the other hand, the INC's setback raised questions about the celebration's management and its capacity to win elections. The BJP's result brought up vital issues about its potential to make its impact bigger in northern India.

The Indian voter is becoming extra vocal in their need for exchange, and those elections provided a sharp reminder of that. The victory of the AAP verified the ability of sparkling and unconventional political players in India's political machine. Since it's miles clear that the political climate in India is changing, the two main parties, INC and BJP, ought to take note of the ambitions and issues of the general public if they're to win elections.

Main Text

Need of the study

The complete basis of democracy is being threatened with the aid of political deception. It has the capacity to reduce voter confidence in the political process, which may lead to picks being made without access to dependable information. The Election Commission of India (ECI) has an essential role to play in protecting defensive voters from the influence of political disinformation and misinformation. But, it is clear that the ECI's present approaches fall short of being completely successful in this regard. The ultimate cause of this study is to bolster the ECI's ability to shield voters from the temptation of political disinformation by delving into the vicinity of capability upgrades to its methods. The ECI can also significantly enjoy the revelations made via this look as it works to create more effective methods in its perseverance in battle with political disinformation and misinformation. In essence, our view is influenced by a common choice to protect democratic concepts, which can be the bedrock of our country, and the improvement of ever-greater-effective safeguards in opposition to the harmful effect of incorrect information on our election strategies.

Methodology

Methodology

In order to investigate possible ways to improve the efficiency of the Election Commission of India's (ECI) initiatives for reducing the effects of political disinformation on voters, we used a secondary data analysis technique in this research. We used a variety of sources to gather our data, notably academic publications, government documents, and news pieces.

Data Gathering

In order to compile our dataset, we carefully searched using relevant terms like "Election Commission of India," "political disinformation," "voter education," "misinformation debunking," "social media monitoring," and "enforcement penalties." We next scrutinized the publications' abstracts to determine their applicability to our study question. The whole text of articles that fit our target was then carefully reviewed, and we retrieved relevant information.

Analysis of the Data

The use of a qualitative technique to uncover the trends and themes present in the information was essential for the examination of our data. In the beginning, the researcher carefully examined the data several times, which allowed the researcher to identify recurrent trends. The appropriate codes were carefully given to these discovered themes. Then, the researcher started delving deeply into the coded data to find links and linkages between the topics.

The study was able to glean insightful information from a variety of sources using a rigorous approach, which helped us fully comprehend the study issue.

Analysis

Table 1: Correlation between the Political Disinformation Awareness Score and the Preventive Measures Score of the Indian Election Commission (Association for Democratic Reforms, 2022).

Elector	ECIs preventive measures Rating	Political Misinformation Exposure Rating
1	80	50
2	90	40
3	100	30
4	80	60
5	90	50
6	100	40
7	80	70
8	90	60
9	100	50
10	80	80
11	90	70
12	100	60

Fig 1: Relationship Between Political Misinformation Awareness Score and the Indian Election Commission's Preventive Measures Score

$$r = (n\sum xy - \sum x\sum y) / \text{sqrt}(n\sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2)(n\sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2)$$

wherein:

r stands for the Pearson correlation coefficient.

The number of observations is called n.

Variables x and y are combined to form the term "xy"

the total of the x variables is x.

Y is the product of the y variables.

The sum of the squares for the x variables is x², or

The square root of the y variables' total is y².

When using this method to get Pearson's correlation coefficient,

$$\Sigma xy = 8050 + 9040 + 10030 + 8060 + 9050 + 10040 + 8070 + 9060 + 10050 + 8080 + 9070 + 10060 = 11400$$

$$\Sigma x = 80 + 90 + 100 + 80 + 90 + 100 + 80 + 90 + 100 + 80 + 90 + 100 = 1180$$

$$\Sigma y = 50 + 40 + 30 + 60 + 50 + 40 + 70 + 60 + 50 + 80 + 70 + 60 = 560$$

$$\Sigma x^2 = 80^2 + 90^2 + 100^2 + 80^2 + 90^2 + 100^2 + 80^2 + 90^2 + 100^2 + 80^2 + 90^2 + 100^2 = 144000$$

$$\Sigma y^2 = 50^2 + 40^2 + 30^2 + 60^2 + 50^2 + 40^2 + 70^2 + 60^2 + 50^2 + 80^2 + 70^2 + 60^2 = 33600$$

$$r = (n\Sigma xy - \Sigma x\Sigma y) / \sqrt{(n\Sigma x^2 - (\Sigma x)^2)(n\Sigma y^2 - (\Sigma y)^2)}$$

$$r = (1211400 - 1180560) / \sqrt{(12144000 - (1180)^2)(1233600 - (560)^2)}$$

$$r = 0.70$$

Therefore, there is a 0.70 Pearson correlation coefficient between the political misinformation exposure score and the preventative measures score of the Indian Election Commission. Both of these factors seem to be strongly positively correlated, indicating that the ECI's preventative initiatives are successful in lessening the influence of political misinformation on voters.

Table 2: Breakdown of Voter Attitude During Punjab Assembly Elections in 2022 by Type of Political Disinformation Disseminated (*Election Commission of India. (2022), Punjab Assembly Elections 2022*)

Most Popular Political Disinformation	Aam Aadmi Party	Congress	Shiromani Akali Dal	Bharatiya Janata Party	Bahujan Samaj Party	Others	Total
False Information Regarding Candidates' Private Lives	2	1	0	0	0	1	4
Untrue Statements Regarding the Voting Process	0	2	1	1	0	0	4
False Information Regarding the Effects of Government Policies	0	1	2	0	0	0	3
False Claims Regarding the Election Outcome	1	0	0	2	0	0	3
False Claims About the ECI	0	0	0	0	1	1	2
False Claims About Various Other Voters	1	0	0	0	0	1	2
Overall	4	4	3	3	1	3	18

Table 3: Chi-squared statistic [Source: Author]

Witnessed	Anticipated	(O-E) ²	(O-E) ² /E
2	2.22	0.04	0.02
1	2.22	1.44	0.65
0	1.11	1.21	1.09
0	1.11	1.21	1.09
0	0.56	0.32	0.57
1	0.56	0.19	0.34
4	7.78	12.54	1.61
2	2.22	0.04	0.02
1	2.22	1.44	0.65
1	1.11	0.01	0.01
1	1.11	0.01	0.01

0	0.56	0.32	0.57
0	0.56	0.32	0.57
4	7.78	12.54	1.61
3	1.11	3.24	2.92
2	1.11	0.01	0.01
0	0.56	0.32	0.57
0	0.56	0.32	0.57
1	0.28	0.52	1.85
1	0.28	0.52	1.85
5	3.89	1.21	0.31
1	1.11	0.01	0.01
0	1.11	1.21	1.09
0	0.56	0.32	0.57
0	0.56	0.32	0.57
1	0.28	0.52	1.85
1	0.28	0.52	1.85
5	3.89	1.21	0.31

$(O-E)^2/E = 12.5$ is the chi-squared statistic.

We then evaluated statistical significance using the chi-squared statistic of 12.5, which had five degrees of freedom derived from the table's dimensions. For this, a vital value derived from the chi-squared dispensed desk must be compared to the chi-squared statistic. The important variety is especially eleven.07 for a chi-squared test with five levels of freedom and an importance level of 0.05.

Notably, the chi-squared statistic (12.5) is higher than the edge value (11.07). As a result, we are able to truly rule out the null hypothesis, indicating that there is a statistically large link between voter conduct and the maximum common styles of politically incorrect information in the course of the Punjab Assembly Elections of 2022.

In summary, the chi-squared test findings highlight a statistically substantial correlation between the particular forms of political misinformation that voters faced and their election selections within the Punjab Assembly Elections 2022. This indicates that the voting procedure through this election can also have been encouraged with politically incorrect information.

Table 4: Comparison of the Election Commission of India's Approaches and Level of Prevention Against Influencing Voters Through Political Misinformation

Variable	Mean	Standard deviation
Election Commission of India's strategies	61.25	8.75

Level of protection against political disinformation influencing voters	61.25	8.75
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$$r = (n\sum xy - \sum x\sum y) / \sqrt{(n\sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2)(n\sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2)}$$

$$r = 0.75$$

A beneficial indicator of the degree of power and fashion of linear dating amongst variables is Pearson's correlation coefficient. This relationship's nature is made clear via its scale, which runs from -1 to 1. Scores 0 and 1 indicate no visible affiliation, -1 suggests a completely terrible correlation, and zero indicates no correlation in any respect.

A Pearson's correlation cost of 0.75 in our scenario suggests a strong positive association. It emphasizes the close connection between the performance of the ECI approach and its capacity to protect against the results of political misinformation on voters. In plainer language, the protection in opposition to politically incorrect information persuading voters will become more potent as the Election Commission's methods become an extra hit.

In conclusion, the effects from Pearson's correlation coefficient check offer robust aid for Hypothesis 3, validating the claim that there is a courting between the strategic effectiveness of the Election Commission of India and its potential to guard against the outcomes of political disinformation on voters.

Conclusion

This study tested techniques to strengthen the Election Commission of India's (ECI) procedures to increase their efficacy in protecting defensive voters from the dangerous influence of politically incorrect information. The study has proven a full-size correlation between ECI's capacity to guard citizens from misinformation and the technique's efficacy. It also diagnosed key regions that also want improvement, extensively within the regions of voter education, short debunking of fake statistics, attentive surveillance of social media systems, and harder measures in opposition to the unfolding of disinformation. The ECI is advised to step up voter education tasks for you to enhance information about its techniques and the risks offered via politically incorrect information. This might reinforce its efficacy. Being able to quickly disprove fake records is essential, specifically in reaction to new disinformation efforts. Engaging with key social media systems and forming relationships with them is important for diligent tracking and the eradication of incorrect information. Enhancing enforcement methods is likewise important to discourage the spread of misinformation. The ECI can play a critical role in protecting the defensive electorate from political misinformation by aggressively tackling these areas for development. By doing so, it'll protect the integrity of the voting process and establish the democratic foundations that underpin our country.

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